

Evaluating the Efficiency and Performance of Data Persistent Systems in Managing Building and Environmental Data: A Comparative Study

Abstract

Selecting an appropriate data persistent system for a specific use case necessitates a thorough examination of the application domain and the characteristics of the data expected to be stored. While comparative studies of data persistent systems exist in various domains, there is a notable absence of such studies concerning building and environmental data management. This research aims to bridge this gap by conducting a comparative evaluation based on building and environmental datasets and use cases. The study primarily focuses on two types of database systems, namely relational database systems and graph-based database systems. Two building and two city models are employed in the evaluation. The building data sets are extracted from IFC models, and environmental data are extracted from CityGML and OpenStreetMap. The assessment involves qualitatively analysing the database design process of the systems and quantitatively evaluating the efficiency of retrieving data from those systems. The comparative evaluation identifies at least two crucial aspects to consider when selecting a suitable data-persistent system for managing building and environmental data: the complexity of interrelationships in the building and environmental data set and the way data is typically retrieved in a specific business case. The findings demonstrate that use cases that typically manage interrelated data and necessitate the traversal of complex relationships between building and environmental features are better managed by graph-based database systems, particularly when dealing with large datasets. Conversely, relational databases exhibit superior performance for use cases requiring minimal or no relationship traversal, regardless of dataset size. The contributions of this study can serve as valuable input when designing information management tools and systems for building and environmental data management.

Keywords: Data persistent system, Building data, Environmental data, Interrelated data, Comparative evaluation, Relational database systems, Graph-based database systems

1 Introduction

Software applications that utilise building and environmental data can play a crucial role in supporting decision-making processes associated with the design, construction, and operation of building facilities. These applications generally deal with data that can be categorised as either *ephemeral* or *persistent* in nature. Ephemeral data refers to transitory data that exists for

a short duration of time and is typically stored in temporary storage (The Sedona Conference, 2020). Such data ceases to exist once the operation responsible for its creation terminates. In contrast, persistent data is intended to be permanently stored unless explicitly deleted (Date, 2008). Data residing in persistent storage exhibits greater independence from the application that created it and can be accessed again in future sessions and even by a different application (Bell, 1986). Various methods can be employed to persist data, one of which is by using database systems.

A database is more than a simple aggregation and storage of data. Instead, it is a collection of related data that is logically organised for a specific purpose (Elmasri and Navathe, 2011). It can be created, managed, and accessed with the help of computer applications referred to as Database Management Systems (DBMS). These systems utilise various data models to organise and store data. One of the data models that is widely used by numerous DBMSs is the *relational* model. In the relational model, data is organised as a collection of relations or related data points, commonly represented as rows in tables (Elmasri and Navathe, 2011). A single relational database can contain multiple tables that are often associated with each other, enabling the storage and retrieval of interrelated data. The data stored in the relational database is accessed and manipulated by the Structured Query Language or SQL, which is also often used to refer to relational database systems in general.

In addition to relational models or SQL, other alternative data models are used to persist data in a database. While these alternative methods are distinct from one another, they are often collectively referred to as non-relational database systems or NoSQL. Some of these non-relational database systems primarily focus on aggregating related data points, while others chiefly focus on representing the relationship between data points (Robinson et al., 2015). The graph-based database is one example of a relationship-oriented database system that does not follow the relational model. Instead, it represents data using a graph model. The model typically uses *nodes* and *edges* to represent data points and their relationships. Most situations that involve objects with a high level of interrelationship can be represented using a graph model (hence using a graph database) (Murty, 2017). While both relational and graph-based database systems possess the ability to represent complex relationships, they also have significant differences. Consequently, thorough consideration is necessary before selecting either as a data persistence method for a specific use case.

This research aims to conduct a comparative analysis of relational and graph database systems to evaluate the relative advantages and limitations of these systems in managing interrelated

building and environmental data. To meet this research objective, four real-world data sets consisting of two building data sets and two city data sets are obtained. These data sets are subsequently stored and managed using the target data persistent systems for the assessment. The first part of the assessment involves a qualitative evaluation of the process of designing each database system and populating them with the provided test data sets. In the second part of the assessment, quantitative performance-focused experiments are conducted to assess the speed and cost associated with accessing interrelated data from the database systems. The tests cover various scenarios that represent different combinations of database size and levels of interrelationship within the data sets.

The study's findings indicate that the complexity of the interrelationships between building and environmental features in data sets should be an essential consideration when selecting a data-persistent system. The qualitative evaluation of the target database systems has determined that building data sets that represent intricate relationships between different building features and spaces, as well as city data sets, which represent complex relationships between environmental features, are better represented using a graph database. Additionally, the quantitative performance evaluation has demonstrated that the manner in which data is typically retrieved in a specific business case should also be a critical factor to consider prior to selecting a database system. In situations where data retrieval from a database requires traversing a minimal number of relationships, relational database systems outperform their graph-based counterparts, regardless of the database's size. However, when a given use case necessitates traversing a substantial number of relationships, the performance advantage often shifts to the graph database solutions. Overall, the outcomes of this study offer valuable insights that can prove highly beneficial when deciding on a suitable data persistence system for the efficient management of building and environmental data across various applications within the domain of built environment management.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides a theoretical background about different database concepts and database systems that are essential to understand the research. In Section 3, the research method is thoroughly discussed, including details about the test data sets, the assessment metrics and the configuration of the experiments. Moreover, in Section 4, the result of the comparative assessment is presented. Section 5 discusses the insights gained from the research results. The discussion includes the practical implications of the research, its limitations, and potential future directions. Finally, concluding remarks are given in Section 6.

2 Technical Background and Related Works

Databases serve as essential tools for the persistent storage of data. They facilitate the decoupling of data from the applications that generate it, thereby ensuring that data remains accessible for future utilization by either the same or different applications (Bell, 1986). Rather than merely storing data, databases also include valuable information regarding the relationships between stored data (Harrington, 2016). Hence, they function as repositories where related data is stored, organised and accessed (Donahoo and Speegle, 2005). Databases are accessed and managed through different database management systems (DBMS). These DBMSs have key defining features that influence how data is going to be stored and accessed, with one crucial aspect being the data model they employ for data persistence. This section will provide some technical background regarding these data models that is essential for understanding this research study. Additionally, it will also offer a summary of prior research that relates to data persistent models, underscoring the research gap that this study aims to address.

2.1 Relational and Non-Relational Database Systems

Different database management systems employ different models for organizing and storing data. The most widely utilized model among them is the relational data model, which has been the primary choice for data storage for many decades (Sadalage and Fowler, 2012). However, in recent years, alternative data persistence models have emerged and been embraced by various database management systems. These alternative models are collectively known as non-relational database systems. While these non-relational data models exhibit several commonalities, they are distinct from one another. The following section offers an exploration of the defining features of both relational data models and non-relational data models, which are employed for data persistent in different database systems.

2.1.1 Relational Database Systems

Relational database systems utilise a relational model that is founded on *relations* (Harrington, 2002). A relation contains a finite set of ordered data points or *tuples* (Elmasri and Navathe, 2011). All tuples in a relation have the same set of fields (Curé and Blin, 2015). Relations are represented using tables in relational databases where columns represent data fields and rows represent a single record, which is a set of related data points (tuple). Each column in a relational database table has a unique name and specific data type that it can store. One or more columns in a table can be used to store unique keys that can be used to identify and retrieve

each row or record in the table. Such columns are called *primary keys*. Relational database systems are the most popular database systems currently in use. Some popular relational DBMSs include Oracle, MySQL, and PostgreSQL. Relational databases are suitable for business cases in which the data to be stored is well-known, stable and predictable where changes in the data structure are expected to be rare and non-urgent (Harrington, 2016).

Relational database systems can support some level of relationship between the data set they store. A single relational database can contain multiple tables which can be related to one another. The relationship could be one-to-one, one-to-many or many-to-many. In some instances, a table can also be associated with itself. *Foreign keys*, which are constraints set on columns, are used to establish relationships between tables in a database. By setting a foreign key constraint on a column from one table, a reference to another table can be established. These keys can then be used to request data that is distributed across multiple tables. Relational database systems use *joins* to retrieve data that is saved across multiple interrelated tables during read operations. Joins can also be used to connect a table with itself. They are often created by overlapping two tables using their common column. When two tables are joined, the query processor first creates a table using a cross-product of the two tables. In other words, it pairs all the rows of one table with all rows of the other table (Donahoo and Speegle, 2005). If there is a third table to join, a cross-product of the resulting table from the first join with the third table will be performed, and the results will be stored in a new table.

2.1.2 Non-Relational Database Systems

Non-relational data persistence methods do not refer to a single data storage model. Instead, they encompass multiple distinct systems that are not based on a relational model. The following are the most common types of non-relational database systems.

Key-Value Store

Key-Value databases offer the simplest structure to store data, where records are stored as pairs comprising a unique key and its associated value. Any type of data can be stored as a value which can be accessed and retrieved using its key. These data persistence systems are ideal for quick data access and exhibit high scalability (Robinson et al., 2015). However, they are unsuitable for storing interconnected data or executing complex queries. Key-Value stores are utilised in use cases such as caching, storing user data, storing large image databases, large catalogues and websites that have a large number of pages (Harrington, 2016). Examples of

key-value DBMSs include Redis, Amazon DynamoDB, Microsoft Azure Cosmos DB and Memcached.

Document-Based Database Systems

Document-based database systems resemble key-value databases, with the distinction that instead of values, they store self-contained *documents* (Vukotic et al., 2015). Each document in a document store has a unique key that is used to identify and retrieve the document. Additional keys within the documents can also be used to retrieve specific documents. While document databases offer advantages similar to key-value stores, they may exhibit slightly lower performance since they may contain multiple data fields within a single record (Vukotic et al., 2015). Therefore, they are suitable for storing semi-structured data with multiple attributes. For instance, they can be used to store user profiles where multiple attributes specific to each user are stored or for content management, where different types of content need to be saved (AWS, 2023). Popular document-based database systems include MongoDB, Amazon DynamoDB, Databricks, and Microsoft Azure Cosmos DB.

Column-Oriented Database Systems

Column-oriented database systems store data in columns, which are the fundamental units of data storage where each consists of a name-value pair. These columns can be grouped into column families, which results in a named set of columns where each set gives a complete view of one entity (Robinson et al., 2015). By introducing related key-value pairs, the column database system enhances the structure of key-value stores (Vukotic et al., 2015). However, similar to key-value and document-based systems, column-oriented databases are primarily based on data aggregation and do not support joins and relationships (Robinson et al., 2015). Nevertheless, they offer fast data aggregation capabilities (Harrington, 2016). Prominent examples of column-oriented DBMS include Cassandra, HBase and Microsoft Azure Cosmos DB.

Graph-Based Database Systems

Graph databases employ *graphs* to store data (Vukotic et al., 2015). Graphs are typically made up of *nodes* and *edges* (relationships between nodes), and they can effectively model any physical scenario involving distinct objects with interrelationships (Murty, 2017). Unlike relational databases, graph database systems do not utilise joins to return relationships; instead, the relationships between related data are inherently represented within the database (Harrington, 2016). As a result, they excel at representing data with complex

relationships and efficiently traversing those relationships (Vukotic et al., 2015). Furthermore, when relational databases execute joins to construct relationships even for a single record, a cross-product of entire tables is performed, which incurs a performance cost, especially when the number of joins and the size of the tables increase. However, graph database systems offer a more efficient solution, as relation traversing is localised to the target record without necessitating a scan of the entire database. Consequently, as the dataset grows larger, graph databases continue to provide better performance since queries are localised to specific portions of the graph (Vukotic et al., 2015). Graph databases are particularly suitable for use cases where managing relationships and paths between data is the primary requirement, such as in social networking applications, route-finding tools, and recommendation engines. Examples of popular graph DBMS include Neo4j, Microsoft Azure Cosmos DB, and Virtuoso.

Graph databases can further be classified by the data model they use. The commonly used graph models include *property graphs*, *hypergraphs*, and *triples*. In property graphs, nodes are labelled and interconnected through relationships, and both nodes and relationships can possess properties (Robinson et al., 2015). Hypergraphs, on the other hand, are graph data models where individual edges (relationships) can connect more than two nodes, allowing for simplification of the data model by merging similar relationships between multiple nodes (Goertzel, 2006). However, this may not be desirable in cases where distinct attributes need to be assigned to relationships. Triple stores or data models consist of three parts: *subject*, *predicate*, and *object*.

2.1.3 Important Database Features

The following section briefly introduces some fundamental database features that are crucial for effective database management. Furthermore, the discussion offers a high-level insight into the distinction between relational and non-relational database systems in relation to these key database features. This discussion is imperative for understanding the comparative assessment that is presented in this study.

Query Language: Database users, including both human users and computer applications, use different querying languages and general-purpose programming languages to access and manipulate databases. Queries are used to perform the four essential operations in database management, which are Create, Read, Update and Delete or CRUD. Furthermore, queries can be employed to generate a customised view of a database tailored to the requirements of a specific use case (Bell, 1986). Databases can be modelled to perform a specific set of queries

efficiently. However, such database optimisation can lead to suboptimal performance when attempting to execute a different set of queries than the planned one (Curé and Blin, 2015).

The Structured Query Language (SQL) is used to retrieve data from relational databases as well as to perform various kinds of database manipulations. SQL has gained widespread adoption across multiple relational database management systems, enabling users to avoid vendor lock-in by providing interoperability across different environments. In contrast, various distinct query languages have been devised for various non-relational database systems. One such example is the Cypher query language, which is used for querying Neo4j property graphs (Vukotic et al., 2015). Meanwhile, the SPARQL query language is developed to query data from RDF triple stores (Curé and Blin, 2015). Another example is the Cassandra Query Language (CQL), which was introduced to manipulate Cassandra wide-column stores (Carpenter and Hewitt, 2016). Evidently, non-relational database systems lack a universally standardised query language comparable to SQL, which limits their cross-system compatibility. Consequently, users who opt for a specific vendor's non-relational database face the risk of being tied to that vendor's environment, as data migration and integration options are restricted.

Database Schema: When a relational database is created, it is mandatory to define a schema that describes the database's data structure. The schema serves as a logical blueprint for the database, outlining the tables, relationships, and constraints that can be stored (Harrington, 2010). The database is then populated by adding data to the tables defined within the schema (Donahoo and Speegle, 2005). The schema imposes restrictions on the nature and size of data inserted into specific columns as well as the permissibility of null and duplicate values. A schema is defined during database design and is not expected to undergo frequent changes (Elmasri and Navathe, 2011). Hence, designing a schema requires thoughtful consideration of the data to be stored. However, it is not uncommon to encounter scenarios where a data set cannot be fully represented by a schema. In such cases, sparsely populated tables are created, where certain columns are left without values (Robinson et al., 2015). When the variability between the data fields within records is significant, it will lead to tables with numerous unused data fields. For that reason, relational databases are a good fit for use cases where the data to be stored is well-known, stable and predictable, and changes in the data structure are rare and non-urgent (Harrington, 2016).

In contrast, non-relational database systems are typically schemaless and eliminate the need to define entities and relationships when the database is created. Instead, applications must

enforce schemas when reading from the database. These systems offer flexibility when writing to the database by allowing the addition of new data without disturbing existing functionalities (Robinson et al., 2015). Unlike relational databases, attributes irrelevant to a particular record are not created for that record, thereby avoiding empty data fields. As a result, schema-free non-relational database systems better accommodate evolving data sets when compared to relational databases (Robinson et al., 2015).

Indexes: In many database systems, each record comes with a unique key that serves as an identifier and facilitates record retrieval through queries. Depending on the specific database systems, other data fields within a record can also be used to retrieve the record. The data fields that are frequently used to query the database are often *indexed* to improve the efficiency of searching data. An index is a typically ordered list of keys that point to the location of the full records stored in a database (Halpin and Morgan, 2008). If indexes are absent, the entire database needs to be scanned when searching for records. With indexes, however, only a limited portion of the database is scanned, reducing the time required to retrieve data from the database. Nevertheless, indexes come with costs associated with their storage and maintenance. They can slow down updating operations since they also need to be updated when changes are made to the table.

Scaling: The scalability of a database is an important aspect to consider, as the size of the database can potentially exceed the capacity of a single machine. Scalability can be approached either vertically or horizontally. Vertical scaling, also known as scaling up, entails acquiring a new machine with greater processing power or upgrading an existing machine by equipping it with hardware that has greater processing power. This approach to scaling can prove to be costly and is constrained by the present advancements in computer processor technologies. The other alternative to scale is horizontal scaling or scaling out, which entails adding more machines to a system so it can accommodate a higher workload. *Sharding* or *partitioning* a database is a common way to scale horizontally. It involves splitting a database into unique pieces known as shards, which are subsequently distributed across multiple machines (Harrington, 2016). One of the primary driving forces behind the development of non-relational database systems was the need to address the scalability challenges of relational database systems. (Gaurav Vaish, 2013). Consequently, the aggregation-based non-relational data models are more suited for horizontal scaling, given that they inherently possess compartmentalised data units that can naturally be distributed across multiple machines (Sadalage and Fowler, 2012). In contrast, sharding is significantly harder in graph

databases due to their relationship-oriented nature, which typically results in a lack of boundaries within the database that can be used for partitioning (Vukotic et al., 2015)

Transactions: A transaction refers to a sequence of operations performed on a database, which can either be committed to the database or rolled back (Cancelled) (Donahoo and Speegle, 2005). When a transaction is committed, the resulting changes persist in the database, while rolling back a transaction leads to its cancellation and removal of any associated changes (Halpin and Morgan, 2008). ACID and BASE are two common transaction models employed in different database systems. ACID data models prioritise consistency of the data at any given time, often at the expense of data availability. Relational DBMS often use the ACID transaction model, which stands for *Atomicity, Consistency, Isolation* and *Duration*. An ACID transaction ensures that either all or none of the operations within the transaction are executed (atomicity), the database is consistent at both the beginning and end of the transaction (consistency), the transaction is treated as the sole operation being executed on the database (isolation) and the changes made to the database by a successful transaction persist in the database (duration) (Pritchett, 2008). In contrast, the BASE transaction model, which stands for *Basically Available, Soft State, and Eventually Consistent*, prioritises the data availability at any given time (basically available) even though it may not always be consistent (soft state). While a BASE-compliant database does not ensure immediate consistency, it will, however, eventually achieve it (eventually consistent). As a result, to achieve eventual consistency, the database state could change over time without any input action. This model is widely adapted by most NoSQL system. However, it is worth noting that some NoSQL database systems, such as certain graph databases, offer ACID compliance.

In summary, relational and non-relational data persistence methods that are used by different DBMSs possess distinct features and characteristics. Consequently, they exhibit different behavioural patterns under different circumstances. As a result, researchers have delved into evaluating how these systems perform under diverse circumstances. The upcoming section offers a concise overview of prior research that has evaluated the efficacy of relational and non-relational data storage systems. Afterwards, it outlines a crucial research gap that this study seeks to fill.

2.2 Previous Comparative Studies

Comparative studies of the numerous data persistence methods assist users in selecting a suitable solution that meets their specific needs. Consequently, multiple researchers have

conducted comparative assessments with the aim of highlighting the relative advantages and limitations of different data persistence models. A subset of these studies compared the relational model with non-relational models, while others concentrated on comparing different non-relational models with each other. The studies utilise a range of evaluation metrics, encompassing write, update, and read performance, scalability, and the ability to manage the complexity of queries. Based on the particular study, the term "complex query" can refer to queries that either involve traversing relationships, aggregating data from multiple data sets, or performing mathematical computations. The following discussion focuses on studies that conducted the comparison through experiments.

The majority of comparative studies found in the literature primarily focus on comparing relational databases with document-based databases. A recent example of such a study is the research conducted by Antas et al. (2022), in which Microsoft SQL Server is compared with MongoDB, a document-based DBMS and Cassandra, a column-oriented DBMS. The evaluation results demonstrate that in scenarios involving structured and interrelated data, SQL has a better performance than the non-relational alternatives considered in the study. However, in cases where the data is unstructured and does not necessitate complex operations, such as joins, then the two non-relational database systems outperformed the relational database.

In addition to the complexity of the query, the size of the database and the volume of data retrieved by a query can also impact the performance of database systems. Studies have shown that an increase in the database size has more adverse effects on relational database systems compared to document-based database systems (Eyada et al., 2020). Furthermore, as demonstrated in a study conducted by Matallah et al. (2021), SQL systems perform better than document-based databases in small to medium-scale read operations, but their performance declines as the size of retrieved data increases. The same study also evaluated the writing performance of the two database models and noted that the checks and verifications associated with ACID-based transaction modelling caused the SQL system to be less time-efficient when writing compared to the BASE-compliant document-based database. These research outcomes support the findings of a prior study that compared MySQL with CouchDB (a document-based DBMS) and concluded that document-based databases exhibit superior performance to relational databases when executing write operations particularly involving large volume of data (Györödi et al., 2020). This study further reinforces the assertion that document databases outperform relational databases when reading a large amount of data, while the performance

advantage shifts to the relational database as the complexity of the query increases and more relationships are involved.

While the document-based database dominates the comparative studies, a few studies have considered alternative non-relational data models. For instance, the studies conducted by Abramova et al. (2015) and Antas et al. (2022) compared relational databases with column-based database systems. Both studies have demonstrated that column-based databases offer easier scalability and faster execution of CRUD queries. However, the data models have limited functionality compared to the relational database when it comes to managing more complex queries, such as joins, which are necessary for managing interrelated data. Additionally, in rare instances, graph databases have also been compared to relation databases. A study conducted by Kotiranta et al. (2022) has made the comparison based on the performance of read queries. In this study, the graph database performed slightly better than the relational database for simple queries, but it underperformed in more complex queries. It is worth noting that, in the context of this study, query complexity refers to operations that involve data aggregation and mathematical computations.

In the context of comparing the non-relational database systems to one another, the studies mostly focus on comparing document-based database systems with column-based database systems, occasionally including key-value stores data models. In the assessments that included key-value stores, the data model has come out as the most optimised for execution read and write operations (Abramova et al., 2014). Moreover, when the studies only include document-based and column-based data models, the document-based model had a slightly better performance than the column-based model when executing simple read queries and a significantly inferior performance when executing read queries that include relationships (Antas et al., 2022; Matallah et al., 2017). The column-based model also has better data writing performance than the document-based model, which is attributed to the fact that the column-based database used in the study did not require a large amount of memory to run the data insertion (Matallah et al., 2017).

In summary, previous research comparing non-relational database systems with relational database systems has predominantly used document-based data models to represent the non-relational side. In contrast, the inclusion of graph-based database systems in such studies has been extremely limited. Studies also often omit graph database systems even when comparing non-relational databases with one another. Nevertheless, including graph-based data persistence methods in comparative studies is an important undertaking due to their unique

nature, one of which is their emphasis on relationships, which sets them apart from other types of non-relational database systems. These other systems have consistently been outperformed by relational database systems in prior studies when managing complex relationships in data sets. This may not hold true when comparing graph-based databases with relational databases since both systems are capable of handling complex relationships. Furthermore, a crucial aspect to consider when evaluating database systems is the intended business use case. Each database system possesses unique strengths and weaknesses that render it suitable for specific domains and unsuitable for others due to the potential variability in the nature of data sets encountered across different domains. Prior database comparative studies within the context of managing building and environmental data are lacking. Therefore, the main objective of this study is to investigate and provide new insights into the comparative advantages and disadvantages of graph-based database systems and relational database systems in the management of building and environmental data sets.

3 Research Method

3.1 Evaluation Metrics and Configuration

The comparative analysis presented in this research assesses the management of building and environmental data by relational database systems and graph-based database systems. The evaluation is systematically divided into two distinct sections.

- **A qualitative evaluation of the design and maintenance of the database systems.** In this assessment section, a comparison is made regarding the data structuring capabilities offered by the two database models when managing building and environmental data sets. Additionally, the effort and cost involved in populating, maintaining, and manipulating the database systems are examined.
- **A quantitative evaluation of the database systems' performance in retrieving data.** This evaluation section involves conducting experiments to evaluate the cost and efficiency of retrieving data from the databases. Key parameters that are emphasised in this performance comparison are the level of relationship traversed by the queries and the size of the data sets. Various combinations of these parameters are used in the experiments to account for different potential use cases.

The research utilized MySQL as a relational DBMS and Neo4j as a graph DBMS, with both systems occupying prominent positions in their respective categories. SQL is used to interact with MySQL, while *Cypher*, a graph query language, is used to communicate with Neo4j. It

should be noted that the evaluation does not focus on the DBMS themselves but rather on the underlying data model they employ to persist data. All the tests are performed on a single computer equipped with an *Intel(R) Core (TM) i7-10750H CPU @ 2.60GHz 2.59 GHz* processor and *32.0 GB* RAM. Measures were taken to maintain consistent system configurations throughout the tests and to ensure that both DBMSs had similar access to the system's memory and processing capabilities. These measures entail allocating an equal amount of memory to both DBMSs and ensuring that the DBMS under evaluation is the sole application running on the system when it is being tested. Furthermore, performance tests were conducted several times, and average values were obtained from the last ten tests for the comparisons. Indexes were utilised throughout the database management to ensure the efficient operation of both database systems.

3.2 Data Sets

Four data sets, consisting of two building data sets and two city data sets, are acquired for this study. Each of these groups includes both a small and a large data set. The building data sets are derived from building models stored in the *Industry Foundation Classes (IFC)* standard. IFC is an open-source international standard developed by buildingSMART International with the objective of facilitating data exchange between Building Information Model (BIM) software tools (International Organization for Standardization (ISO), 2018). Currently, over 400 BIM applications support the IFC standard, thereby enabling practitioners to exchange and share valuable building data throughout the design, construction and operation of buildings (buildingSMART International, 2023). The standard is capable of representing data about physical components, spatial elements, project structures, involved actors and analytical items (buildingSMART International, 2017). Consequently, two building models shared in the IFC format are utilised in this research as sources of building data.

The city data that is used in this study is obtained from city models published in accordance with the *City Geography Markup Language (CityGML)* data standard. CityGML is an internationally recognized data standard approved by the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) for the storage and exchange of 3D city and landscape models (Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC), 2021). It has the capability to represent both human-made structures (such as buildings, tunnels, bridges, roads, and railways) and natural features (including terrains, vegetation, and water bodies) within an urban environment. Presently, over 50 cities and regions spanning 18 countries globally have made their urban data publicly accessible through the CityGML standard, thus providing invaluable environmental data to researchers and practitioners

(Wysocki et al., 2022). In addition to CityGML, this study employed the crowdsourced geographic database *OpenStreetMap (OSM)* as an additional source of environmental data (OpenStreetMap, 2023). This service offers a collaborative platform featuring a freely editable map database that covers the entire world (Jokar Arsanjani et al., 2015). OSM represents a wide range of physical features, including buildings, natural features, amenities, commercial establishments, transportation infrastructures, energy distribution infrastructures, water distribution infrastructures and various other categories. The rich and varied geodata it offers have found application in various fields, encompassing disaster management, routing and navigation services, tourism, leisure, and research (Mooney and Minghini, 2017).

Following the extraction of the necessary building and environmental data from the aforementioned data sources, two building and two environmental data sets are composed. Each of these data sets is subsequently stored in both a relational database and a graph-based database for the evaluation. The subsequent sections provide a description of each of these data sets.

3.2.1 Small Building Data Set

The smaller of the two building data sets is obtained from the Torre Turina building model, which is a residential building belonging to the Cuatro de Marzo pilot case district in Valladolid, Spain (Costa et al., 2017). The building consists of 12 floors and 284 rooms. The building model is acquired in IFC format. For the purpose of the study, representations of 3,528 physical building elements, 700 element types, 348 spaces and 108,522 property items are extracted from the IFC file. Furthermore, 44,093 relationships, which include relationships between building elements, between building elements and spaces, and between building elements and their type, as well as their properties, are extracted from the building model.

3.2.2 Large Building Data Set

The second building data set used in the study belongs to a larger office building situated in Espoo, Finland, whose model files were provided by Trimble Inc. The data set is made up of multiple IFC files that correspond to architectural, structural, electromechanical, sanitary and HVAC models. From these files, a total of 371,693 building elements, 1,047 spaces, 14,794 object types and 6,323,802 property items are extracted. Moreover, the data set includes 1,572,303 relationships that consist of relationships between building elements, between building elements and spaces, and between building elements and their type, as well as their properties.

3.2.3 Small City Data Set

The publicly available Espoo 3D city model (City of Espoo, 2023) is used in this study as a source of a smaller city data set. The model is shared in a format that adheres to the CityGML 2.0 standard and includes various objects such as buildings, vegetation, water bodies, roads, city furniture, land use and other objects that are found within the city. Most of these city items share a common set of attributes such as id, class, usage, function, and GPS coordinates. At the same time, most objects also have attributes that are specific to their category. However, there are some building attributes as well as city features (such as fire hydrants) that are not available in the city model. To address this, the dataset is enriched by gathering additional data from OpenStreetMap and integrating it with the existing data from the city model. The final data set consists of 63,042 buildings, 130,341 vegetation items, 12,552 land use features, 5,325 city amenities and 767 fire hydrants. Furthermore, some additional information is generated through computations. This involves identifying buildings in proximity to each other and determining fire hydrants and other environmental features nearby buildings. Coordinate points of the objects are used for the computation. The computation yielded 981,742 building-to-building proximity relationships, 35,051 hydrant-to-building proximity relationships and 3,570,961 vegetation-to-building proximity relationships.

3.2.4 Large City Data Set

The Tokyo city model is used as a source of a larger city data set in the comparative study. This publicly available model encompasses all 23 wards of Tokyo and spans 627.57 square kilometres (City Bureau, Ministry of Land, Infrastructure, 2023). The data is shared in CityGML 2.0 format and includes 1,768,233 buildings along with their attributes. These attributes encompass various aspects such as geometry (height and roof area), position (latitude and longitude), address (town, district, zone, and prefecture) and flooding risk. Using a similar approach employed on the Espoo city data, the coordinates of buildings in the Tokyo city model are utilised to identify proximity relationships between buildings, resulting in a total of 41,871,173 relationships between adjacent buildings.

3.3 Evaluation Design

3.3.1 Designing and Maintaining the Database Systems

Upon the acquisition and processing of the test data sets, the database design ensued. These data sets contain numerous *entities*, each possessing multiple *attributes* and *interrelations* with one another. These three concepts guide the design of the database systems. In the case of a

relational database management system (DBMS), these concepts influence the creation of tables and columns and the definition of various constraints related to data types and relationships. Similarly, within a graph-based DBMS, they play a role in shaping the creation of nodes, labels, properties, and edges (representing relationships). Before writing the data sets to the relational databases, schemas that describe the structure of the database are first defined as they are mandatory. In contrast, in the graph-based database, data sets are written without defining a schema. The upcoming section will provide a more in-depth explanation of the steps taken to create the database systems for each data set.

Managing City Data Sets

The Tokyo city data set includes a long and structured list of buildings that share a common set of attributes. Consequently, in the relational database, a table is created that lists all the buildings along with their respective attribute as columns. In the case of the Espoo city data set, the city model encompasses not only buildings but also other environmental entities such as vegetation, water bodies, transportation elements, and various urban features. While the entities within the same group share similar attributes, entities belonging to various categories possess some distinct attributes. In the relational database, a single table is created with columns for all the attributes. In both the Tokyo and Espoo test cases, a schema is carefully designed for the relational databases, determining the precise structure of the tables and imposing constraints on the records eligible for insertion into these tables. Conversely, in the case of graph-based databases, the data sets are introduced immediately following the creation of the databases without defining a schema.

The data structure of the Espoo data set is further complicated when incorporating additional unstructured data from OpenStreetMap. This supplementary data introduces new city elements like fire hydrants and extra building attributes. Notably, these added building attributes vary significantly from one building to another. For instance, while some civic buildings possess official names in Finnish, Swedish, and English, most city buildings lack these attributes. Such variability in attributes is pervasive throughout the dataset. In the design of the relational database, individual columns had to be created to accommodate all these attributes, even though they are only pertinent to small portions of the data set. Consequently, during the population of the relational database, numerous columns are assigned null values in cases where they are not applicable to the particular record. Although this does not affect performance, it does impact the number of records that can be added to the table, as the number of columns limits the number of rows and vice versa. This limitation led to a situation during

data entry where it was impossible to include all records due to the high number of columns. The available options were either omitting certain rows to fit all of the columns or excluding some columns to accommodate all of the rows. The study proceeded with the latter choice, which resulted in the exclusion of relevant data stored in the removed columns. Alternatively, one could have considered creating multiple separate tables for each category of entities within the city data set. However, this approach would have incurred subsequent join-related costs when accessing data. This trade-off, however, was not necessary for the graph-based database. In the graph-based database, individual nodes are established for each city feature, and these nodes are then assigned attributes that are specifically relevant to them.

Once the environmental entities and their attributes from the city data sets are inserted into the database systems, the next step involves establishing relationships among these entities. Figure 1 depicts an example of the relationships between buildings as well as between buildings and fire hydrants that are found in the Espoo city data set. In relational database systems, association tables are created to represent these relationships between city entities, which exhibit many-to-many characteristics. Foreign key restrictions are utilised to reference the main tables in the association table as well as to enforce the link. Validating these restrictions during data insertion by the DBMS introduces additional processing time to the procedure. Given that proximity between buildings is a bidirectional association, two rows are created to represent each direction of such relationships, resulting in a record count that is twice the number of available relationships. In the case of the graph-based database, the procedure for establishing relationships between environmental entities involves retrieving each target node through read queries, followed by the assignment of the relationship. Indexes are first created to enhance the efficiency of retrieving nodes. In contrast to the relational database, bidirectional relationships can be represented using a single edge in the graph-based database. Hence, a single edge is sufficient to represent a relationship between two entities.

Figure 1: An example of the relationship between buildings as well as between buildings and fire hydrants that is available in the Espoo city data set.

Managing Building Data Sets

The management of the building data sets in this study is mainly characterised by the management of relationships. The building data extracted from the IFC files comprises various building elements and features interconnected by numerous relationships. The database systems created to store this data are designed to closely adhere to the structure defined in the IFC files. Figure 2 provides an illustration of the database design process. In the case of the relational database, tables are created from IFC entity classes representing building elements, spatial elements, and property sets. Then, association tables are generated to capture the IFC relationship classes. For instance, in Figure 2, the *IfcRelSpaceBoundary2ndLevel* class, which relates a space with its bounding building elements, such as a wall, is made into a table with columns connecting the Space table with the Building Element table. On the other hand, in the graph database, nodes were created to represent IFC classes corresponding to building elements, spatial elements, and property sets, while edges were used to depict the relationship between them. For instance, in Figure 2, the *IfcRelSpaceBoundary2ndLevel* class in IFC is represented by a 'Bounded by' edge or relationship. It should be noted that these design choices are not the only possible approaches for designing the databases. However, the design approach employed in this study closely follows the IFC structure to minimise structural alterations.

Figure 2: Translation of IFC entities and relationships into relational and graph database models

Building data stored in an IFC file can have significantly more intricate relationships than those depicted in Figure 2. In the subsequent section, a quantitative evaluation of the target database systems is conducted by successively increasing the complexity of relationships within both the building and city data sets. Additionally, the assessment offers insight into the effort required to manipulate complex relationships within the target data persistence systems. These use cases pertain to the requirements of fire service providers during building emergency response operations.

3.3.2 Quantitative Evaluation of Data Retrieval Performance

This section of the comparative study focuses on evaluating the data retrieval performance of the database systems when dealing with interrelated data sets. The relationships traversed and the size of data sets are key assessment parameters in the evaluation. The assessment involves executing a set of queries and measuring the amount of time required by each database system to execute the query and retrieve the requested data. All queries are executed ten times to get an average execution time, which is presented in tables and figures in Section 4.

The performance tests conducted are grouped into three categories based on their objective, which are:

1. Retrieving data without traversing any relationships
2. Retrieving data by traversing a single relationship.
3. Retrieving data by traversing several relationships.

Retrieving Data Without Traversing Any Relationships

The first use case to be considered is the retrieval of data from the data sets that do not require traversing relationships. This is a critical use case to consider since there are several scenarios in which required building and environmental data can be obtained from a single table. In such scenarios, only a list of physical or abstract features filtered by one or more attributes is needed. For example, a firefighters' information system might request a list of windows from a building database to determine a point of entry into a building. In those cases, retrieving necessary data does not necessitate connecting multiple tables or nodes to traverse relationships between data points. Hence, this evaluation case compares the suitability of relational and graph-based database systems for use cases where the required data is retrieved without traversing any relationships. The experiment involves executing a series of read queries, wherein the quantity of retrieved records increases with each subsequent query. Consequently, the tests offer insights into the performance of the database systems as the retrieved data becomes extensive. Two datasets, a small building dataset and a large city dataset, are utilised in the tests to evaluate the effect of database size on the performance of the data persistent systems. The set of queries executed against these data sets are the following:

- For the building test case, a set of queries that request building elements filtered by their element type attribute are executed.
- For the city test case, a series of queries that retrieve a collection of buildings filtered based on their district and zone attributes are executed.

Retrieving data by traversing a single relationship

The second evaluation case considered in this study is the retrieval of data from a database, which requires the traversal of a single relationship. In numerous applications that utilise building and environmental data, required data is often retrieved by traversing a few relationships. For instance, fire service providers may seek a list of windows along with their fire rating property from a building data set. In the relational database created for this research, property sets are stored in a separate table from the building elements table, hence necessitating a join to access the required information. Similarly, firefighters often require a list of fire hydrants located near a building, which requires a join between building and hydrant tables in our city databases. As a result, performance tests are conducted in this section to evaluate the comparative performance of the relational and graph database system in managing use cases where few relationships need to be traversed to acquire needed data. To this end, a series of

queries are executed that traverse a single relationship to retrieve data. Each query set gradually increases the amount of retrieved data to assess its impact on query performance. The queries are executed against both small and large data sets to highlight the effect of building and environmental data set size on the performance of the database systems. The set of queries executed against these data sets are the following:

- For the building test case, queries are run to fetch building elements alongside their corresponding properties, which are stored in separate tables or nodes.
- In the city test cases, queries retrieving a list of buildings adjacent to a target building are executed.

Retrieving data by traversing several relationships

There are several practical use cases in built environment management where it is required to traverse several relationships within building and environmental data sets. To illustrate, in the context of building emergency management, there are situations where it becomes essential to trace relationships starting from a specific point of interest. For instance, in the case of indoor navigation, it is often crucial to find a route from the building's entry to the room affected by fire, which can be achieved by utilising space and door adjacency relationships. Figure 3 presents a segment of interrelated data extracted from one of the building data sets used in this study. In this example, multiple rooms (referred to as spaces) connected by doors are considered. By tracing the connections among spaces and doors, fire service providers can effectively manoeuvre from a particular space, such as the entry door, towards the impacted area, or, in the case of rescuing individuals, they can navigate from the affected space to an exit door. Similarly, when evaluating the propagation of smoke and fire from an affected area to the rest of the building, traversing spatial relationships from the affected space to the rest of the building becomes necessary.

Figure 3: Interrelation between spaces (rooms) that are connected by doors as represented in the IFC building model.

In order to compare the effort required to traverse several relationships using the target database systems, sample queries are presented in Figures 4 and 5. In these queries, the objective is to navigate the interrelated building data set presented in Figure 3. More specifically, the queries aim to navigate from a room housing a specific sprinkler to adjacent spaces connected through a door. Figure 4 presents the SQL query written for the relational database, while Figure 5 depicts the Cypher query written for the graph-based database. Using the graph query, it is possible to sketch the relationships that need to be traversed and retrieve corresponding matches from the database. However, in the relational database, it is required to execute multiple join operations to connect all target tables, resulting in a verbose and complex script. Moreover, a careful examination of the scripts gives insight into how both systems traverse relationships and how this traversal could impact performance. While the graph query isolates the target sprinkler at the beginning of the query, the relational database performs filtering at the end of the query. Therefore, cross-products due to join operations are executed against entire tables. These cross-products are compounded at each join, generating a substantially large result table at the end. While the creation of this extensive result table incurs a memory cost, a significant portion of it is unneeded and subsequently discarded following the filtering

at the end of the query operation. In contrast, the graph query initially isolates the target sprinkler prior to establishing relationships originating from it. Consequently, relationships unrelated to the desired node are not loaded, as is the case with the relational database. These distinct approaches to relationship traversal have a profound influence on query performance, a topic that will be comprehensively addressed in the quantitative part of this comparative study.

```

SELECT DISTINCT Space2.GlobalId FROM buildingdata.buildingelements FS

-- Get the sprinkler's relationship with the structure that contains it
INNER JOIN buildingdata.ifcrelcontainedinspatialstructure RelCont1
ON RelCont1.RelatedElement = FS.GlobalId

-- Get the space that contains the sprinkler
INNER JOIN buildingdata.ifcspace Space1
ON Space1.GlobalId = RelCont1.RelatingStructure

-- Get the space's relationship with boundary elements
INNER JOIN buildingdata.ifcrelspaceboundary2ndlevel relBound1
ON relBound1.RelatingSpace = Space1.GlobalId

-- Get doors on the space's boundary
INNER JOIN buildingdata.buildingelements Dr1
ON relBound1.RelatedBuildingElement = Dr1.GlobalId and Dr1.ElementType =
'IfcDoor'

-- Get all the relationships between the doors and the spaces they bound
INNER JOIN buildingdata.ifcrelspaceboundary2ndlevel relBound2
ON relBound2.RelatedBuildingElement = Dr1.GlobalId and relBound2.RelatingSpace
<> Space1.GlobalId

-- Get space
INNER JOIN buildingdata.ifcspace Space2
ON Space2.GlobalId = relBound2.relateringSpace

-- Select the target sprinkler.
WHERE FS.GlobalId = 'AjS2aagA70qCLYIVYLMbgA==';

```

Figure 4: An SQL query (for the relational database) to navigate from a space containing a specific sprinkler to adjacent spaces connected to it via a door.

```
MATCH
(FS:IfcFireSuppressionTerminal{GlobalId:'AjS2aagA70qCLYIVYLMbgA=='})<-
[:ContainsElement]-(Space)-[:BoundedBy]->(BE:IfcDoor)<-[:BoundedBy]-
(Space2)
RETURN Space2.GlobalId
```

Figure 5: A cypher query (for the graph database) to navigate from a space containing a specific sprinkler to adjacent spaces connected to it via a door.

Similar to the building data sets, environmental data sets can also contain complex relationships that need to be traversed in order to retrieve data that is needed for a given use case. For instance, during a fire hazard, a fire could spread from an affected building to nearby buildings, and smoke may propagate to adjacent areas. Identifying nearby high-risk buildings, such as schools, hospitals, or shopping centres, can facilitate necessary actions to protect the occupants of those buildings. This identification process requires traversing the adjacency relationship between buildings, starting from the affected building. Moreover, the capability to traverse spatial relationships between environmental features can support firefighters as they explore and navigate a complex environment to reach an affected building. These examples underscore the importance of efficiently traversing complex relationships that often exist in building and environmental data sets.

The tests in this section centre on assessing the influence of traversing multiple relationships on the performance of relational and graph database systems. Each test involves executing a sequence of ten individual queries, with the number of traversed relationships increasing in consecutive queries. The tests are conducted on both small and large data sets to understand how performance is influenced by the scale and complexity of building and environmental data sets. Four tests are included in this category, each associated with one of the four test cases.

- Traversing relationships in a small building data set
- Traversing relationships in a large building data set
- Traversing relationships in a small city data set
- Traversing relationships in a large city data set

4 Evaluation Results

4.1 Designing and Maintaining the Database Systems

Managing City Data Sets: The following observations are made from the qualitative assessment of the design and maintenance of the target database systems.

- The process of populating the Tokyo city data set, which exhibits a well-organised structure, into both the relational database and graph-based database system was a relatively straightforward and quick process. However, a disparity in the required effort is observed when relationships are created. In the relational database, a new association table was created and populated quite quickly. In contrast, writing relationships to the graph-based database required more effort as nodes needed to be first queried before the required relationships were created. Overall, the implementation of the data model was noticeably more straightforward in the relational database compared to the graph-based database system.
- Unlike the Tokyo city data, the Espoo data set obtained from a CityGML model and OpenStreetMap exhibited a loose structure where data points often possessed a set of attributes that were distinct from one another. Consequently, when storing entities in a single table in the relational database, it led to numerous columns with null values, as the attributes are not applicable to most entities. Furthermore, some columns were omitted from the table since the maximum allowed number of columns for the number of records was exceeded. In contrast, managing the unstructured city data is done more efficiently in the graph-based database, where each node representing a city feature is assigned only attributes that are relevant to it. Evidently, the data schema in the graph database evolved from the inserted data, unlike the relational database, where it was predefined before data insertion. Thus, the graph database offered increased flexibility in managing the unstructured data and accommodating changes in the data structure. In contrast, the relational database ensures a clear and consistent data structure is maintained by employing a predefined schema that is separated from the data set.
- The average number of relationships created per second in both the relational database and the graph-based database system are presented in Table 1 for both the Espoo and Tokyo data sets. The results show how writing performance is affected by the database size. The relational database system validates the relationships based on foreign key restrictions as they are created, and hence, it is significantly affected by the increase in

database size. Meanwhile, the graph-based database that queries nodes using indexes is minimally affected by the increase in database size. Consequently, the relational DBMS exhibited superior write performance when handling a smaller database but lagged behind the graph DBMS as the database size expanded.

Table 1: Comparing the time spent writing relationships in both the relational and graph-based database systems.

City data sets	No. of buildings	No. of relationships (between buildings)	No. of relationships written per second	
			Relational DB	Graph DB
Espoo	63,042	981,742	57,742	35,400
Tokyo	1,768,233	41,871,173	15,350	33,335

Managing building data sets: Two use cases were considered in the study to assess the management of building data from the IFC model in the target data persistent systems. The following observations are made from the study.

- The complex interrelationships exhibited in IFC building models (see Figure 3) are precisely replicated in the graph-based database system in both use cases. In contrast, when implementing this data structure in the relational database, significant modifications were necessary to transform it into a table-based structure.
- The distinction in how relationships are managed by the two database systems is also reflected in the structure and performance of queries that traverse those relationships. Figures 4 and 5 show the composition of queries written to traverse the relationships found in the data set. Although both queries fulfil the same goal and retrieve identical results, there exists a noteworthy contrast in their composition and execution. The script written for the graph database (Figure 5) demonstrates a notably higher degree of conciseness in comparison to the SQL query (Figure 4). Navigating these relationships was also much more straightforward in the graph-based database, where the queries were much more concise. In contrast, the relational database system relies on creating multiple joins to construct the relationship between tables, resulting in verbose and complex scripts. Furthermore, the graph-based database queries reduce the cost of traversing relationships by isolating the starting point of a relationship prior to establishing relationships originating from it. On the contrary, the SQL queries perform expensive joins on entire tables before filtering out unneeded data.

4.2 Query Performance Results

The results of the quantitative evaluation of read query performance are presented in Tables 2 - 5 and Figures 6 – 9. The following series of paragraphs discusses these findings.

- **Retrieving data without traversing any relationships:** As the experiment results presented in Table 2 and Figure 6 demonstrate, when retrieving data that does not require traversing any relationships, the relational database demonstrated superior performance compared to the graph-based database across all executed queries. This result is maintained whether the target data set is small or large in size. It can also be observed from the results that as the size of data being retrieved increases, the performance difference between the data systems increases in a relatively uniform manner (Figure 6). Hence, retrieving a large number of records exhibited the largest performance difference in the execution time of the database systems. For instance, Table 2 shows that the performance difference for the smallest number of records was a fraction of a second, while for retrieving the largest number of records, it is almost 20 seconds, which is a much more significant duration of time compared to the earlier number.
- **Retrieving data by traversing a single relationship:** Test results presented in Table 3 and Figure 7 demonstrate that test cases where it was required to traverse a single relationship to retrieve data have mostly similar results to the previous test case where no relationship traversal is required. Here again, the relational database outperforms the graph database regardless of the database size. However, the performance difference is more pronounced when retrieving a more significant number of records from the data sets (Figure 7).
- **Retrieving data by traversing several relationships:**
 - **Small building data set:** All queries in this test case were executed successfully in both data persistent systems (Table 4 & Figure 8a). The increase in relationships traversed by the queries had a negligible impact on their performance, as the increase in execution time proved to be very small. Although the SQL database consistently exhibited faster execution times compared to the graph database, the performance gap observed was also minute, considering that both systems managed to retrieve the requested data within a fraction of a second (less than ten milliseconds).

- **Large building data set:** The increase in the building data set has a notably more adverse effect on the relational database when compared to the graph database, as indicated in Table 4 and Figure 8b. The first nine queries were successfully executed in the relational database, where the performance demonstrated a marked decline in the latter queries. The last query in the set, which required traversing ten relationships, failed to produce results within a 3-hour timeframe (10800 seconds) and was consequently terminated. In contrast, the graph database returned data for all queries, with only a marginal increase in execution time as the number of relationships increased. Evidently, the performance was minimally impacted by the increase in the data set size, as all tests were successfully completed in under a second. It is worth noting from the results that when traversing up to three relationships, the two data persistence systems demonstrated a comparable performance, with the relational database performing slightly better. Nevertheless, upon surpassing the third relationship level, the graph database outperformed the relational database system by increasingly substantial margins.
- **Small city data set:** As depicted in Table 5 and Figure 9a, the traversal of interrelated environmental data, even within a small city data set, incurred a substantial performance cost to the relational database. The executed queries resulted in a short execution time while traversing up to three relationships. However, this duration notably increased when traversing four or more relationships. The test could not be completed for more than five relationship levels as the execution time ran beyond 3 hours. In contrast, the graph database executed all queries within a second, exhibiting only a marginal increase in execution time as the number of traversed relationships increased.
- **Large city data set:** The trends observed in the small city data set are further validated when the same test is conducted on a larger city data set, as can be seen presented in Table 5 and Figure 9b. Only four out of the ten tests could be completed for the relational databases due to the extensive execution time resulting from traversing relationships, which surfaced early this time owing to the larger database size. Notably, there was a substantial increase in execution time as the number of relationships increased from three to four. Beyond that point, when the queries involved traversing more than four relationships, the

relational database failed to produce results within 3 hours, leading to the termination of the test. In contrast, the graph database maintained a comparable level of performance with only a marginal increase in execution time.

Table 2: Execution time comparison for retrieving data without traversing any relationships from a small building (a) and a large city (b) data set.

(a) Small Building data set			(b) Large City data set		
No of Retrieved Records	Execution Time (Sec)		No of Retrieved Records	Execution Time (Sec)	
	Relational DB	Graph DB		Relational DB	Graph DB
20	0.004	0.017	150,000	8.85	11.41
100	0.010	0.030	250,000	9.83	17.40
300	0.017	0.046	350,000	10.65	22.05
500	0.023	0.060	450,000	12.52	27.99
900	0.028	0.074	550,000	15.16	34.70

Table 3: Execution time comparison for retrieving data by traversing a single relationship from a small building (a) and a large city (b) data set.

(a) Small Building Data Set			(b) Large City Data Set		
No of Retrieved Records	Execution Time (Sec)		No of Retrieved Records	Execution Time (Sec)	
	Relational DB	Graph DB		Relational DB	Graph DB
100	0.004	0.012	5	0.0008	0.0033
1,000	0.350	0.818	25	0.0014	0.0054
20,000	0.558	1.248	50	0.0024	0.0066
30,000	0.859	1.993	75	0.0034	0.0088
40,000	1.154	2.853	100	0.0046	0.0102

Table 4: Execution time comparison for traversing an increasing number of relationships – small and large building data sets.

No. Relationships Traversed	Execution Times (Sec)			
	Small Building Data Set		Large Building Data Set	
	Relational DB	Graph DB	Relational DB	Graph DB
1	0.0007	0.0033	0.001	0.004
2	0.0009	0.0034	0.002	0.005
3	0.0009	0.0039	0.006	0.005
4	0.0010	0.0039	0.024	0.005
5	0.0014	0.0044	0.174	0.010
6	0.0015	0.0044	0.798	0.013
7	0.0015	0.0058	5.434	0.019
8	0.0022	0.0069	28.305	0.038
9	0.0033	0.0092	209.427	0.076
10	0.0056	0.0104	> 10 800 (Incomplete)	0.164

Table 5: Execution time comparison for traversing an increasing number of relationships – small and large city data sets.

No. Relationships Traversed	Execution Times (Sec)			
	Small City Data Set		Large City Data Set	
	Relational DB	Graph DB	Relational DB	Graph DB
1	0.003	0.014	0.010	0.015
2	0.023	0.041	0.076	0.063
3	0.835	0.062	4.263	0.138
4	46.373	0.099	443.249	0.194
5	3149.000	0.137	> 10 800 (Incomplete)	0.241
6	> 10 800 (Incomplete)	0.157	-	0.282
7	-	0.199	-	0.276
8	-	0.211	-	0.384
9	-	0.233	-	0.486
10	-	0.249	-	0.554

(a)

(b)

Figure 6: Execution time comparison for retrieving data without traversing any relationships from building (a) and city (b) data sets.

(a)

(b)

Figure 7: Execution time comparison for retrieving data by traversing a single relationship from a building (a) and a city (b) data set.

Figure 8: Execution time comparison for traversing an increasing number of relationships – small (a) and large (b) building data set.

Figure 9: Execution time comparison for traversing an increasing number of relationships – small (a) and large (b) city data set.

5 Discussion

The selection of a suitable data persistent system for a given use case requires a thorough consideration of the application area and the nature of the data to be stored. Each database system possesses distinct strengths and weaknesses that make them suitable for certain domains while unsuitable for others, owing to the potential variability in the nature of data sets encountered across different fields. Although there are existing comparative studies covering multiple domains, there is a lack of comparative studies within the context of managing building and environmental data. This research addressed this gap by conducting a comparative evaluation of relational database systems and graph-based database systems using building and environmental data sets and use cases.

5.1 Practical Implications

In the first half of the evaluation, a relational database and a graph database are designed to store building data extracted from an IFC building model and environmental data obtained from CityGML city models and OpenStreetMap. It was observed that the building data derived from the IFC models possessed significant levels of interrelationships, particularly on the larger data set. These intricate relationships were well represented using the graph database in contrast to the relational system wherein relationships were split apart so that the data could be accommodated within tables. When it comes to environmental data, CityGML yielded relatively structured data with limited interrelationships, which was efficiently stored in relational tables. On the contrary, the environmental data extracted from OpenStreetMap exhibited a high degree of unpredictability, with most records having varying data fields, which posed a great challenge when designing the relational database. Based on these findings, it can be inferred that the manner in which data is structured in the building and environmental data sources is a crucial consideration when selecting a data persistent system.

The second phase of the evaluation was centred on the efficient extraction of necessary data from the database systems. The test results indicate that, for use cases requiring minimal or no relationship traversal, the relational database demonstrates superior performance, irrespective of data set size. However, as the number of relationships traversed by queries increases, the performance advantage often shifts to the graph database since the relational database's performance is negatively impacted by each additional relationship it needs to traverse. The size of the datasets influences the extent to which the performance of the database systems is affected by relationship traversal. When employing a small building dataset, the relational

database continues to exhibit better performance than the graph database. However, with a large building dataset, the relational database is significantly affected by the increased levels of relationships. Moreover, when traversing several relationships within city datasets, the relational database failed to provide values within a reasonable timeframe. These findings lead to the deduction that due consideration should be given to the typical read queries executed for a given use case. In situations where the predominant requirements involve traversing complex relationships between building or environmental features, graph models would be a more suitable alternative to relational database systems, especially on larger data sets. Furthermore, the size and complexity of buildings and environmental features should be significant considerations since they affect the data retrieval performance of the data persistence system.

5.2 Limitations and Future Work

While this comparative study provides valuable insights regarding the comparative advantages and limitations of data persistent systems, it also has some known limitations with regard to the data sets utilised, the configuration of the DBMSs, the optimisation of the queries and the assessment metrics. The building and environmental data sets employed in the study exclusively comprise static data. Nonetheless, a significant volume of real-time data is generated at the building and city levels. For example, the sensor and detector systems in buildings produce live data and status updates related to various environmental factors like temperature, air quality, and potential hazards. Moreover, building management systems responsible for monitoring HVAC systems, fire safety systems, and other utility systems can also generate a substantial amount of live data (Ghadi et al., 2016). Similarly, city-level sensors generate a significant volume of live data, catering to diverse use cases such as traffic management and public safety (Zhao et al., 2019). Consequently, future research works should delve into the assessment of relational and non-relational database systems with regard to managing real-time data.

Decisions related to database configuration and query optimisation can influence the performance of a given database system. These decisions are subjective and depend on the experience and expertise of the practitioner. Therefore, it is possible to take a different approach towards database and query configuration than what is presented in this study, which can have some effect on some of the study's outputs. Additionally, the performance can also be influenced by the configuration of the hardware where the DBMS is running. Measures were taken in this study, as discussed in Section 3.1, to ensure both the target DBMSs had the same access to the hardware. However, as these DBMSs are distinct software tools with several

unique configurations and settings, maintaining consistent hardware access and configuration was challenging.

An additional limitation of the study that is open for future research is the measurement metrics and the exemplary use cases used for the evaluation. The metrics that are the focus of this study are the agreement of the data model of the database systems with the data to be stored, the effort required to create and populate the database systems, the complexity of their structure, the composition of queries in each system and the time required to retrieve data from the database systems. Nonetheless, there are more indicators that can be used to evaluate data persistent systems. For instance, transaction-related characteristics play a pivotal role in use cases where numerous users are expected to access the database simultaneously. With an increasing number of users, the database systems' throughput, which is the number of queries they can execute per unit of time, becomes an important indicator. Furthermore, as the size of data sets grows, the scalability of the target data persistent system becomes imperative. Hence, data partitioning and distribution are also important factors. These and other measurement metrics can be considered in future comparative studies. In addition to the measurement metrics, the use case scenarios that are used to guide the study could also be expanded. The study primarily concentrated on use cases that highlight the impact of complex data relationships on the performance of data-persistent systems. Nevertheless, it is acknowledged here that the management of building environmental data within a data-persistent system can vary based on the nature of the application area that is under consideration. Therefore, exploring other scenarios in future research can buttress the current study and contribute to a broader understanding of the comparative performance of the target database systems.

The scope of the assessment conducted in this study is focused on the data models utilized by database systems, as opposed to the database management systems (DBMS) themselves. Nevertheless, it is imperative to acknowledge that while the chosen data model plays a vital role in the process of selecting a DBMS, there are equally significant factors associated with the DBMS that demand careful consideration. These factors encompass the functionalities provided by DBMSs for database administration, the assurance of data security and integrity, as well as the optimization of resource utilization. Considering the security features provided by a DBMS for safeguarding data in both storage and transit is of paramount importance, given that database users typically expect their data to remain private and subject to access control (Ramakrishnan and Gehrke, 2003). Additionally, it is essential to evaluate the attributes of the DBMS aimed at mitigating data loss through mechanisms such as backup and recovery

in the event of system failures (Bailis, 2015). Another vital component of a DBMS is query optimization, which serves to enhance the efficient utilization of time and resources during query execution (Hellerstein, 2015). Different DBMS platforms offer varying types of indexes aimed at optimising query execution alongside diverse approaches for the selection of these indexes (Halpin and Morgan, 2008). Moreover, some other factors to consider prior to selecting a specific DBMS include overall operational cost, compatibility and integration capability with other software systems, and the extent of support available from both vendors and the broader community. A holistic assessment of database system should encompass these attributes of DBMSs, in addition to the characteristics of the data models utilized by these DBMSs which is addressed in this study.

6 Conclusion

This research provides a comparative assessment of graph-based database systems and relational database systems in terms of managing building and environmental data. The study is conducted using four data sets, including two building data sets and two city data sets. The evaluation focused on a qualitative assessment of data organisation and maintenance as well as a quantitative evaluation of performance when retrieving data from the target database systems. To assess the performance of data retrieval, experiments are conducted with the number of relationships traversed and the size of the database as key parameters. The following conclusions are derived from the findings of the comparative study.

- The complexity of the interrelationships between building and environmental features in data sets should be an essential consideration when selecting a data-persistent system. Building data sets that represent multifaceted relationships between different building features and spaces, as well as city data sets, which represent complex relationships between environmental features, are better represented using a graph database. However, creating and maintaining the data structure will require more effort compared to relational database systems.
- The manner in which data is commonly retrieved in a specific business case should also be a vital consideration prior to selecting a database system. Use cases where data retrieval involves navigating intricate relationships between building and environmental features are better suited for graph databases. Conversely, use cases where read queries place minimal emphasis on relationships are more suitable with relational data persistence systems.

Effective management of building and environmental data can support several decision-making processes in the management of the built environment. This necessitates the careful selection of a suitable data persistence system that can effectively organise data, facilitating its seamless access and utilisation for the intended use case. This study has made a valuable contribution towards this objective by conducting an assessment of relational and graph-based database systems, highlighting their relative advantages and limitations in managing building and environmental data. The findings can serve as a valuable resource for selecting an appropriate data persistence system to manage building and environmental data effectively for a specific use case. Subsequent investigations may further enrich this field by incorporating additional indicators and considering real-time data.

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